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AMOC weakening in response to global and regional reductions in aerosol emissions

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Abstract

In response to continued greenhouse gas (GHG) increases, the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) is expected to weaken through the 21st century. However, AMOC impacts associated with efforts to improve air quality are less well understood. Here, eight models from the Regional Aerosol Model Intercomparison Project are examined to quantify mid-21st century AMOC changes resulting from global and regional anthropogenic aerosol and precursor gas (AA) emissions reductions (industrial and biomass burning), by comparing strong air pollution control shared socioeconomic pathway (SSP1-2.6) to a baseline with weak air pollution control (SSP3-7.0). Global AA reductions and subsequent warming yield multi-model mean AMOC weakening of 6% (-0.98 ± 0.40 Sv; $1 \text{ Sv} = 10^6 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$) by the last 12 years of the simulation (2039–2050). This is $\frac{1}{3}$ of the magnitude of the corresponding weakening associated with the high GHG emissions scenario SSP3-7.0. Of the regional perturbations, combined North American and European AA reductions drive the largest AMOC weakening, followed by combined African and Middle

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Eastern reductions and then East Asian reductions, with South Asian reductions yielding non-significant weakening. Across these experiments, AMOC weakening is significantly correlated with the North Atlantic Ocean aerosol effective radiative forcing ($r = -0.95$) and aerosol optical depth response ($r = 1.0$). AMOC weakening under AA reductions is associated with a thermally driven reduction in buoyancy in the subpolar North Atlantic, which is largely driven by surface short-wave radiation increases, consistent with the forcing from AA reductions. Africa + Middle East AA reductions also involve excitation of a negative North Atlantic Oscillation pattern, which contributes to AMOC weakening. Our results show that efforts to improve air quality, particularly around the Atlantic basin but also far away in East Asia, will contribute to future AMOC weakening.

1. Introduction

The Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) represents the Atlantic branch of the global overturning circulation. It is a central component of the climate system, transporting heat, freshwater, carbon and nutrients (Buckley and Marshall 2016). By moving warm, salty water poleward and returning colder, denser water at depth, the AMOC shapes sea surface temperature (SST) patterns and modulates patterns of precipitation and storm tracks. Because it is sustained by a delicate balance of buoyancy forcing (surface heat loss and freshwater fluxes) and wind-driven circulation, the AMOC is sensitive to anthropogenic perturbations (Fox-Kemper *et al* 2021). Understanding how human activities affect the AMOC is therefore essential for projecting near- and long-term climate change, as well as associated risks to ecosystems and societies.

Increasing anthropogenic greenhouse gas (GHG) concentrations provide the dominant long-term push toward AMOC weakening (Gregory *et al* 2005, Cheng *et al* 2013, Weijer *et al* 2020). GHGs warm the surface, enhance upper-ocean stratification, and accelerate high-latitude hydrological cycle changes that increase freshwater input into the North Atlantic via precipitation, runoff and ice melt. These processes act to reduce surface water density and inhibit deep convection, which weakens the AMOC. The IPCC Sixth Assessment Report (AR6) assesses that the AMOC will very likely decline over the 21st century under all shared socioeconomic pathways (SSPs; Fox-Kemper *et al* 2021). This decline is relatively scenario-insensitive until mid-century, with stronger divergence as GHG emissions pathways separate (Weijer *et al* 2020). Multimodel end-of-century AMOC weakening ranges from 24% under SSP1-2.6 (a sustainability pathway leading to low GHGs) to 39% under SSP5-8.5 (a fossil fuel intensive pathway leading to high GHGs).

In contrast to GHGs, anthropogenic aerosols (AAs) through both direct radiative effects and aerosol-cloud interactions (Bellouin *et al* 2020) preferentially cool the Northern Hemisphere (Forster *et al* 2021). This increases North Atlantic surface ocean density via stronger ocean-to-atmosphere heat loss and reduced freshwater flux, thereby strengthening deep convection and opposing GHG-driven AMOC weakening (Delworth *et al* 2005, Delworth and Dixon 2006, Menary *et al* 2013, Hassan *et al* 2021, Robson *et al* 2022, Li *et al* 2023, Allen *et al* 2024). In Coupled Model Intercomparison Project version 6 (CMIP6; Eyring *et al* 2016) historical simulations, aerosol forcing is linked to multimodel mean AMOC strengthening of 10% over 1850–1985, and the model spread is related to a proxy for the strength of the aerosol forcing (Robson *et al* 2022). Moreover, this strengthening is larger than that simulated by CMIP5 simulations, which is consistent with the inclusion of aerosol-cloud interactions in more CMIP6 models (e.g. Booth *et al* 2012). However, AA forcing and/or the AMOC response may be overestimated in CMIP6 (Menary *et al* 2020, Hassan *et al* 2021, Robson *et al* 2022, Needham *et al* 2024, Li and Liu 2025).

AAs are also spatially heterogeneous and little is known about the impact of regional aerosol emissions on the AMOC. Liu *et al* (2024) recently conducted idealized experiments by decreasing solar insolation (a proxy for aerosol increases) by 10% (a very strong perturbation relative to typical anthropogenic changes) in the West (North America and Europe) and separately in the East (East Asia and South Asia). The West perturbation (reversed to mimic the post-1980s decrease in AA emissions there) yielded the anticipated AMOC weakening, consistent with the above studies focused on global aerosol perturbations (e.g. Hassan *et al* 2021). Perhaps surprisingly, the East perturbation (which mimics the increase in AA emissions there) also yielded AMOC weakening. This weakening was associated with a circumglobal teleconnection and a negative North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO)-like pattern, including weakened westerlies over subpolar North Atlantic, leading to a reduction in surface heat loss through changes in turbulent fluxes, and reduced deep water formation. Similar dynamical mechanisms are also highlighted in Diao *et al* (2021) and Li *et al* (2025). In particular, Li and Liu (2025) further support this pathway using idealized ‘10×sulfate’ experiments within the Precipitation Driver and Response Model Intercomparison

(PDRMIP) project (Samset *et al* 2016). Thus, these idealized studies imply that the impact of AAs on the AMOC may depend on the location of the AA forcing, with opposite responses for East Asia and South Asia as compared to other regions.

Through the 21st century, both the magnitude and spatial distribution of aerosol forcing remains uncertain, with most future emissions scenarios yielding AA emissions decreases associated with efforts to improve air-quality (Lund *et al* 2019, Persad *et al* 2023, Samset *et al* 2024). As these efforts are pursued, they will unmask GHG driven warming (Allen *et al* 2020, 2021, Samet *et al* 2025), which may accelerate weakening of the AMOC (Ma *et al* 2020, Hassan *et al* 2022). For example, using four chemistry-climate models with experiments designed to target near-term climate forcer mitigation (ssp370 versus ssp370-lowNTCF), Hassan *et al* (2022) showed that reducing (global) aerosols and related precursors yields AMOC weakening on the order of $\sim 10\%$ by end-of-the-century. The impact of future, regional decreases in AAs remains to be quantified, as do the mechanisms by which AA reductions in different regions affect the AMOC.

The Regional Aerosol Model Intercomparison Project (RAMIP) contains a comprehensive suite of simulations from CMIP6-era global climate models, specifically designed to improve our understanding of the climate effects associated with both global and regional aerosol reductions (Wilcox *et al* 2023). Here, we use eight RAMIP models (each with 10 ensemble members) to quantify the AMOC response to global aerosol reductions in line with realistic near-term policy choices, as well as regional aerosol reductions from four regions. Section 2 briefly summarizes the RAMIP experimental design and models, and also describes our methodologies. Section 3 presents results, including the AMOC response to global and regional AA reductions, the relationship to the aerosol effective radiative forcing (ERF), and the associated mechanisms. Conclusions and discussion follow in section 4.

2. Data and methods

2.1. Model experiments

2.1.1. Coupled ocean-atmosphere transient experiments

Following RAMIP (Wilcox *et al* 2023) protocols, we use pairs of transient (2015–2050) coupled ocean-atmosphere climate model simulations (supplementary table 1), initialized from the end of the CMIP6 historical simulations. The ScenarioMIP ssp370 simulation, which features weak levels of air quality control from the SSP3-7.0 scenario, is used as the baseline. All transient RAMIP simulations include prescribed concentrations of well-mixed GHGs and land use changes from SSP3-7.0. RAMIP perturbation experiments (e.g. ssp370-126aer) use an identical setup to ssp370 but take anthropogenic aerosol and precursor emissions of sulfur dioxide (SO₂), sulfate (SO₄), black carbon (BC), and organic aerosol (OA) from the SSP1-2.6 scenario, which features strong levels of air quality control. Perturbation experiments are conducted for the globe and four regions: Africa and Middle East; East Asia; North America and Europe; and South Asia. Each perturbation features ten ensemble members for each of the eight models (80 total simulations), which represents a balance between computational cost and additional information gained per ensemble member (Monerie *et al* 2022). The corresponding aerosol reduction signals are obtained by subtracting the baseline ssp370 experiment from each of the aerosol reduction experiments (e.g. ssp370-126aer-ssp370) on an annual basis. This yields a difference time series which is used to quantify the magnitude of the response.

2.1.2. Fixed SST (fSST) time slice experiments

To assess the aerosol ERF, we use pairs of RAMIP 30 year time-slice simulations, where SSTs, sea ice concentrations and land use are fixed to preindustrial monthly climatologies (supplementary table 2) (Pincus *et al* 2016, Wilcox *et al* 2023, Allen *et al* 2026). All time-slice simulations feature year 2050 GHGs, ozone and natural emissions from SSP3-7.0. The baseline experiment (piClim-370) also uses year 2050 anthropogenic aerosol and precursor gas emissions from SSP3-7.0. The global aerosol reduction experiment (i.e. piClim-370-126aer) is identical in all ways except it uses year 2050 anthropogenic aerosol and precursor gas emissions from SSP1-2.6. The regional aerosol reduction experiments (e.g. piClim-370-EAS126aer) also use year 2050 anthropogenic aerosol and precursor gas emissions from SSP1-2.6 within the region of consideration (e.g. East Asia) and SSP3-7.0 emissions otherwise. The corresponding aerosol reduction signals are obtained by subtracting the baseline piClim370 experiment from each of the aerosol reduction experiments (e.g. piClim370-126aer).

In both experimental setups, ‘anthropogenic aerosol and precursor gas emissions’ includes both industrial and biomass burning emissions of SO₂, SO₄, BC, and OA. However, the bulk of the emissions decrease is due to industrial (as opposed to biomass burning) emissions, e.g. 99% of the decrease in SO₂

Table 1. RAMIP models and their atmospheric resolution, aerosol scheme, RAMIP data reference and model reference.

Model	Atmos. Res.	Aerosol scheme	RAMIP data references	Model references
CanESM5-1	2.8° × 2.8°	Interactive (bulk)	Fraser-Leach <i>et al</i> (2025)	Swart <i>et al</i> (2019)
CESM2	0.9° × 1.25° 1.9° × 2.5° (piClim)	MAM4 (modal)	Allen (2025)	Danabasoglu <i>et al</i> (2020)
CNRM-ESM2-1	1.4° × 1.4°	TACTIC v2 (modal)	Nabat (2025)	Seferian <i>et al</i> (2019)
EC-Earth3-AerChem	0.7° × 0.7°	TM5 (modal)	O'Donnell <i>et al</i> (2025)	van Noije <i>et al</i> (2021)
MIROC6	1.4° × 1.4°	SPRINTARS 6.0 (bulk)	Takemura (2025)	Tatebe <i>et al</i> (2019)
MRI-ESM2-0	1.125° × 1.125°	MASINGAR mk2r4 (bulk)	Oshima and Koshiro (2025)	Yukimoto <i>et al</i> (2019)
NorESM2-LM	1.9° × 2.5°	OsloAero (modal)	Lewinschal (2025)	Seland <i>et al</i> (2020)
UKESM1-0-LL	1.25° × 1.875°	GLOMAP-mode (modal)	Rumbold <i>et al</i> (2025)	Sellar <i>et al</i> (2019)

emissions under the global perturbation is due to industrial emissions (Allen *et al* 2026). The seasonal cycle of emissions is included in all simulations. GLO refers to the global aerosol reduction signal; AFR refers to the Africa and Middle East aerosol reduction signal; EAS refers to the East Asia aerosol reduction signal; NAE refers to the North America and Europe aerosol reduction signal; and SAS refers to the South Asia aerosol reduction signal.

2.2. Models

Eight RAMIP models performed the transient and time slice simulations and archived the required variables for this analysis. Models include CanESM5-1, CESM2, CNRM-ESM2-1, EC-Earth3-AerChem, MIROC6, MRI-ESM2-0, NorESM2-LM, UKESM1-0-LL (table 1). All eight models include an interactive representation of aerosols (e.g. transport, removal). Seven models include a representation of both aerosol-cloud indirect effects. CNRM-ESM2-1 lacks the Albrecht (aerosol-cloud lifetime) effect. All model data is reinterpolated to a 2.5° × 2.5° grid. ERF analyses are based on all 30 years of the fSST experiments. Analyses based on the coupled ocean atmosphere transient simulations emphasize three 12 year time periods: 2015–2026; 2027–2038; and 2039–2050. In all cases, annual mean data is analyzed.

2.3. AMOC Definition

The AMOC is defined as the maximum annual mean stream function below 500 m at 28° N in the Atlantic Ocean, using the CMIP6 variables msftmz (ocean meridional overturning mass streamfunction) or msftyz (ocean Y overturning mass streamfunction). Similar AMOC changes are obtained with alternative AMOC definitions (e.g. at 40° N). AMOC units are Sverdrup (Sv), which is a unit for ocean current volume transport in 10⁶ m³ s⁻¹.

2.4. Surface density flux (SDF) definition

The SDF indicates the loss or gain of density (buoyancy) of the ocean surface due to thermal (radiation, sensible and latent heat) and saline (sea-ice melting/freezing, brine rejection, precipitation minus evaporation) exchanges (Liu *et al* 2017, 2019, Zhu and Liu 2025). An increase in subpolar North Atlantic SDF is associated with strengthening of the AMOC; a decrease in SDF is associated with weakening of the AMOC. SDF is defined as:

$$\text{SDF} = -\alpha \frac{hfd_s}{c_p} - \rho(0, \text{SST}) \times \beta \frac{wfo \times \text{SSS}}{1 - \text{SSS}} \quad (1)$$

where c_p , SST, and SSS are the specific heat capacity, SST, and salinity, respectively; α and β are thermal expansion and saline contraction coefficients; and $\rho(0, \text{SST})$ is the density of freshwater with a salinity of zero and the temperature of SST. hfd_s represents the net surface heat flux into ocean (positive downward), which has contributions from shortwave (SW) and longwave (LW) radiation, sensible (SH) and latent (LH) heat fluxes, and heat fluxes from sea ice melting and other minor sources. wfo represents net surface freshwater flux into the ocean (positive downward) and has positive contributions from precipitation, runoff and ice melting and negative contributions from evaporation. The first term $-\alpha \frac{hfd_s}{c_p}$ represents the thermal contribution (TSDF); the second term $\rho(0, \text{SST}) \times \beta \frac{wfo \times \text{SSS}}{1 - \text{SSS}}$ represents the saline contribution (SSDF) to the SDF. All SDF responses are reported in units of mg m⁻² s⁻¹.

2.5. Other definitions

The North Atlantic is defined as the region from 20–70° N and 280–360° E. The subpolar North Atlantic, where most of the AMOC feedbacks occur, is defined as 50–65° N and 300–350° E (highlighted by green boxes in our figures).

Model agreement on the sign of the response is indicated when at least 6 of the 8 models agree. When this is not the case, the region is stippled. Uncertainty is quantified as the 90% confidence interval, estimated as $1.65 \times \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{n}}$, where σ is the standard deviation across models and n is the number of models.

3. Results

3.1. North atlantic aerosol ERF and AOD

We first start with an analysis of the ERF (i.e. net change in top-of-the-atmosphere energy flux) from RAMIP fSST experiments, which represent the forced response. Coupled runs include feedbacks, which can be prominent for AMOC-related analyses (e.g. Hassan *et al* 2021, Robson *et al* 2022). Figure 1 shows the multimodel mean North Atlantic aerosol ERF from the fSST experiments, as well as the corresponding time series over the North Atlantic Ocean (20–70° N and 280–360° E). Note that fSST simulations are not transient, as AA emissions are held fixed at 2050 levels (based on SSP3-7.0 for the baseline experiment and SSP1-2.6 for the others), and thus provide an estimate of the aerosol forcing by the end of the coupled ocean atmosphere simulations. All experiments feature an increase in North Atlantic Ocean aerosol ERF (although not significant for SAS). GLO (figures 1(a) and (b)) yields the largest North Atlantic Ocean aerosol ERF at $1.08 \pm 0.33 \text{ W m}^{-2}$, followed by NAE (figures 1(c) and (d)) at $0.61 \pm 0.16 \text{ W m}^{-2}$; AFR (figures 1(e) and (f)) at $0.10 \pm 0.08 \text{ W m}^{-2}$; EAS (figures 1(g) and (h)) at $0.10 \pm 0.08 \text{ W m}^{-2}$; and SAS (figures 1(i) and (j)) at $0.04 \pm 0.11 \text{ W m}^{-2}$. As will be shown below, these ERF values significantly correlate with the AMOC responses over the last 12 years (2039–2050) from the coupled runs, which supports the importance of local (i.e. North Atlantic) aerosol to the AMOC response. Most of the North America + Europe ERF occurs in the mid/high latitudes, whereas AFR yields its largest ERF in the subtropics. EAS and SAS yield weaker and more diffuse ERF, with less model agreement (especially for SAS), but ERF increases are in general largest south of Greenland/Iceland and west of the UK. For example, aerosol ERF over the subpolar North Atlantic (50–65° N and 300–350° E) Ocean increases to $0.18 \pm 0.21 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ for EAS and $0.10 \pm 0.20 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ for SAS, respectively. Qualitatively similar results are generally obtained for North Atlantic Ocean surface downwelling SW radiation and surface net SW radiation (although EAS yields slightly larger values than AFR). For the former, for example, GLO yields increases in North Atlantic Ocean downwelling surface SW radiation of $2.09 \pm 0.58 \text{ W m}^{-2}$, followed by NAE at $0.92 \pm 0.22 \text{ W m}^{-2}$; EAS at $0.34 \pm 0.22 \text{ W m}^{-2}$; AFR at $0.31 \pm 0.16 \text{ W m}^{-2}$; and SAS at $0.04 \pm 0.11 \text{ W m}^{-2}$. Given the considerable distance EAS and SAS are from the North Atlantic, this shows the ability of atmospheric circulation to transport aerosols over large distances.

To more distinctly show the importance of North Atlantic aerosol, including the ability of long-range aerosol transport to this region (e.g. from EAS), supplementary figure 1 shows aerosol optical depth at 550 nm (AOD) responses from the coupled ocean-atmosphere simulations (which includes the temporal evolution of AA reductions). North Atlantic Ocean AOD begins to decrease early in the simulations (i.e. 2015–2026) and in general becomes progressively more negative. By the last 12 years (2039–2050), North Atlantic Ocean AOD significantly decreases in all simulations. GLO again yields the largest decrease at $-13.6 \pm 3.6 \times 10^{-3}$, followed by NAE at $-5.3 \pm 1.1 \times 10^{-3}$; AFR at $-2.8 \pm 0.6 \times 10^{-3}$; EAS at $-2.3 \pm 1.2 \times 10^{-3}$; and SAS at $-1.4 \pm 1.0 \times 10^{-3}$. Both EAS and SAS feature an increase in AOD near west Africa (with mixed model agreement), presumably due to dust feedbacks. Similar North Atlantic Ocean AOD decreases are obtained from the fSST experiments (years 1–30). Anthropogenic aerosols having a relatively short real-world atmospheric lifetime (due to wet and dry removal) of $\sim 4\text{--}7$ d in the lower troposphere. This may be longer in some models, and it depends on the aerosol species (Textor *et al* 2006). UKESM1-0-LL, for example, has a SO_4 lifetime of 5.57 d (Mulcahy *et al* 2020), which is on the upper end of the range shown in AeroCom models of 3–5.4 d (Textor *et al* 2006). Nonetheless, RAMIP simulations suggest some aerosol is transported over relatively large distances (i.e. from EAS to the North Atlantic), likely due to lofting into the upper troposphere.

3.1.1. AMOC Response

Figure 2 shows the multimodel mean Atlantic depth-latitude meridional stream function responses for three time periods (2015–2026; 2027–2038; and 2039–2050) and the corresponding AMOC (maximum stream function below 500 m at 28° N in the Atlantic Ocean) time series for each of the aerosol

reduction perturbations. As defined above, aerosol reduction signals are obtained by subtracting the baseline ssp370 experiment from each of the aerosol reduction experiments (e.g. ssp370-126aer) on an annual basis. This yields a difference time series which is used to quantify the magnitude of the response, i.e. the 2015–2026 response compares the baseline ssp370 experiment with an aerosol reduction experiment over the first 12 years; the 2027–2038 response compares the baseline ssp370 experiment with an aerosol reduction experiment over the middle 12 years; and the 2039–2050 response compares the baseline ssp370 experiment with an aerosol reduction experiment over the final 12 years. In general, the stream function continues to decrease in strength as one progresses through the three time periods (consistent with AOD; supplementary figure 1), with maximum weakening near the climatological maximum stream function (around $30\text{--}40^\circ\text{ N}$ at 1000 m depth). Model agreement (lack of stippling) on this decrease also tends to improve as time progresses. These statements are particularly true for GLO, NAE and AFR. GLO shows acceleration of AMOC weakening from -0.16 ± 0.15 Sv for 2015–2026 to -0.45 ± 0.23 Sv for 2027–2038 and to -0.98 ± 0.40 Sv for 2039–2050. Similarly, NAE AMOC weakening for the three consecutive time periods accelerates from -0.02 ± 0.04 Sv to Sv and to -0.34 ± 0.18 Sv, respectively. AFR AMOC weakening also accelerates from -0.05 ± 0.05 Sv

Atlantic Depth-Latitude Meridional Stream Function [Sv] and AMOC Time Series [Sv]

Figure 2. Multimodel mean Atlantic depth-latitude meridional stream function responses and AMOC time series. Panels show responses for (a)–(d) Global; (e)–(h) North America + Europe; (i)–(l) Africa + Middle East; (m)–(p) East Asia; and (q)–(t) South Asia aerosol reductions. Atlantic depth-latitude meridional stream function responses are shown for three 12 year time periods including (a, e, i, m, q) 2015–2026; (b, f, j, n, r) 2027–2038; and (c, g, k, o, s) 2039–2050. Non-stippled regions indicate at least 6 of the 8 models agree on the sign of the response. Climatological stream function (based on the first time period from 2015–2026 from the baseline ssp370 experiment) is shown as a thin black line in all cross-section panels. AMOC time series includes the uncertainty (gray shading), estimated as the 90% confidence interval across models. Units are Sv.

to -0.19 ± 0.09 Sv and to -0.22 ± 0.14 Sv. Although there is less model agreement, EAS AMOC weakening accelerates from -0.04 ± 0.06 Sv for 2015–2026 to -0.13 ± 0.14 Sv for 2027–2038 and to -0.19 ± 0.18 Sv for 2039–2050. SAS yields AMOC weakening of -0.04 ± 0.04 Sv for 2015–2026, nonsignificant AMOC strengthening of 0.03 ± 0.07 Sv for 2027–2038, and non-significant weakening of Sv for 2039–2050. supplementary figure 2 shows a similar (but stronger) AMOC response under the baseline ssp370 experiment (which features large GHG increases), with 2039–2050 AMOC weakening of -3.0 ± 0.78 Sv.

Supplementary figure 3 shows corresponding plots for the annual mean ocean mixed layer depth (MLD), which exhibits subpolar North Atlantic evolution similar to the AMOC, consistent with weakened convection and reduced deep water formation (Liu and Liu 2013). By 2039–2050, the multimodal mean subpolar North Atlantic MLD decreases in all perturbations (not significant for SAS) at -17.5 ± 8.8 m for GLO; -6.2 ± 3.8 m for NAE; -5.2 ± 4.4 m for EAS; -4.9 ± 2.9 m for AFR; and -1.6 ± 2.0 m for SAS. The corresponding linear correlation (r) with the AMOC responses (across experiments) is 1.0. Thus, perturbations that feature larger decreases in MLD also feature larger AMOC weakening. Furthermore, the correlation between the AMOC and MLD responses across models is significant at the 90% confidence level for each experiment (outside of SAS) at $r = 0.90$ for GLO; 0.99 for NAE; 0.88 for EAS; 0.74 for AFR; and 0.64 for SAS. Thus, models that yield larger decreases in MLD also yield larger AMOC weakening.

Figure 3 emphasizes AMOC responses over the last 12 years of the experiments (2039–2050) for each model and each experiment, as well as the multimodel mean (MMM; black). As mentioned above, GLO (figure 3(a)) yields the largest multimodel mean AMOC weakening of Sv, and all 8 models yield a decrease. This weakening is about $\frac{1}{3}$ as large as the corresponding weakening under the baseline ssp370 experiment (which features large GHG increases) at -3.0 ± 0.78 Sv with all 8 models yielding a decrease. The intermodel AMOC spread under GLO is relatively large with NorESM2-LM yielding AMOC weakening of -1.97 ± 0.32 Sv versus CNRM-ESM2-1 at -0.10 ± 0.20 Sv. NAE (figure 3(b)) yields the second largest multimodel mean AMOC weakening at -0.34 ± 0.18 Sv, and 7 of the 8 models yield a decrease. Similar to GLO, NorESM2-LM yields the strongest NAE AMOC weakening at -0.94 ± 0.24 Sv and CNRM-ESM2-1 is the lone model that yields a nonsignificant response. AFR (figure 3(c)) yields the next largest multimodel mean AMOC weakening at -0.22 ± 0.14 Sv with 7 of the 8 models yielding a decrease. NorESM2-LM again yields the strongest weakening for AFR at Sv. EAS (figure 3(d)) yields the next largest multimodel mean AMOC weakening at -0.19 ± 0.18 Sv with 5 of the 8 models yielding a decrease. As with the above perturbations, NorESM2-LM yields the strongest AMOC weakening for EAS at -0.82 ± 0.39 Sv. Three models, including MRI-ESM2-0, UKESM1-0-LL and CNRM-ESM2-1 yield a nonsignificant response. SAS (figure 3(e)) yields non-significant multimodel mean AMOC weakening at -0.05 ± 0.13 Sv with 5 of the 8 models yielding a decrease. NorESM2-LM continues to yield the strongest AMOC weakening at -0.46 ± 0.35 Sv. Only MRI-ESM2-0 yields significant AMOC strengthening at 0.29 ± 0.21 Sv. We therefore do not find robust evidence for an opposite AMOC response to East Asia or South Asia AA emissions reductions compared to reductions over North America and Europe (as in Liu *et al* 2024).

Figure 4 shows that the multimodel mean AMOC response (2039–2050) across experiments is consistent with the North Atlantic Ocean aerosol ERF (from fSST simulations), as the linear correlation is -0.95 , significant at the 99% confidence level. The ERF from fSST runs is used here to relate the magnitude of the AMOC response across RAMIP perturbations to a quantity that represents the forced response (the coupled runs will include feedbacks, which can be prominent for AMOC-related analyses). Aerosol perturbations that feature larger positive ERF (e.g. GLO; NAE; and AFR) are associated with larger AMOC weakening. Similar results are obtained if surface downwelling SW radiation or net surface SW radiation are used, with correlations of -0.95 . Furthermore, a similar (but positive) correlation is obtained if we use North Atlantic Ocean AOD from the coupled simulations, where $r = 1.0$ (figure 4(b)). The corresponding correlation based on net TOA energy flux from the coupled simulations is also significant ($r = -0.90$; significant at the 95% confidence level). We note that there are only five points in these correlations, which are also heavily influenced by the relatively large GLO responses. All of these results support the importance of North Atlantic aerosol to the AMOC response.

Consistent with prior work (e.g. Weijer *et al* 2020), figure 5 shows that the intermodel spread in the AMOC response (2039–2050) for a given experiment is generally related to each model's AMOC climatology. Here, the climatology is based on year 2015 (as opposed to 2015–2026) from the baseline ssp370 experiment using all realizations (effectively providing 10 years of 2015 climatology). This is to avoid biasing the climatology, since 2015–2026 includes some weakening. We also lack historical data for all ensemble members, which precludes a 12 year present-day climatology. Each experiment yields a negative correlation, which ranges from for GLO (figure 5(a)) to -0.27 for SAS (figure 5(e)). AFR

(figure 5(c)) and SAS (figure 5(e)) are not significant at the 90% confidence level. Thus, models with a stronger climatological AMOC tend to have larger AMOC weakening. The intermodel AMOC spread is less well explained by the intermodel North Atlantic Ocean ERF. Although these correlations are negative (as expected) and significant at the 95% confidence level for GLO and NAE ($r = -0.73$ and, respectively), they are weak and not significant for AFR ($r = 0.03$), EAS ($r = -0.07$) and SAS ($r = 0.12$).

3.2. AMOC mechanisms

Figures 6–10 show multimodal mean annual mean maps (for the three time periods) and subpolar North Atlantic time series for several quantities related to the AMOC, for GLO (figure 6) and each regional perturbation (figures 7–10). The top two rows of each figure show (SST; panels (a)–(d)) and sea surface salinity (SSS; panels (e)–(h)) responses. For the AA perturbations that yield significant AMOC weakening (all except SAS; figure 10), subpolar North Atlantic SST increases through the first two time

periods (2015–2026 and 2027–2038) with maximum warming during 2027–2038, followed by muted warming/cooling (especially south of Greenland/Iceland) during the final 12 years (2039–2050). This behavior is consistent with AA reductions driving warming, which reduces sea surface density and initiates AMOC weakening. This is followed by a **negative** AMOC feedback whereby less heat is transported

poleward (Liu *et al* 2020), muting the AA forced warming (Ma *et al* 2020, Hassan *et al* 2021, 2022, Allen *et al* 2024) as well as the decrease in sea surface density. Compared to the subpolar North Atlantic SST response, the SSS response is delayed, with minimal changes through 2015–2026, and also 2027–2038 in most perturbations (GLO is the exception). By 2039–2050, however, maximum decreases in subpolar North Atlantic SSS occur. This behavior is consistent with a delayed positive AMOC feedback whereby less salt is transported poleward under AMOC weakening, which acts to reduce sea surface density and maintain AMOC weakening. Thus, initial AMOC weakening is consistent with subpolar North Atlantic SST warming (a consequence of the AA reductions), which is subsequently buttressed by the AMOC–salt advection feedback (Stommel 1961, Rahmstorf 1996).

This is further supported by investigation of the subpolar North Atlantic (SDF; panels i–l), which indicates the loss or gain of density (buoyancy) of the ocean surface due to thermal and saline exchanges

(Liu et al 2017, 2019). For each AA perturbation, SDF evolution closely corresponds to the AMOC. By 2039–2050, the multimodel mean subpolar North Atlantic SDF decreases in all perturbations (not significant for SAS) at $-0.28 \pm 0.11 \text{ mg m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for GLO; $-0.08 \pm 0.05 \text{ mg m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for NAE; $-0.06 \pm$

Figure 7. NAE multimodel mean maps and subpolar North Atlantic time series. Panels show responses for (a)–(d) sea surface temperature (K); (e)–(h) sea surface salinity (psu); (i)–(l) surface density flux ($\text{mg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$); (m)–(p) thermal component of SDF ($\text{mg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$); (q)–(t) shortwave radiation component of TSD ($\text{mg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$); (u)–(x) longwave radiation component of TSD ($\text{mg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$); (y)–(bb) latent heat component of TSD ($\text{mg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$); and (cc)–(ff) sensible heat component of TSD ($\text{mg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$). Responses are shown for three 12 year time periods including (a, e, i, m, q, u, y, cc) 2015–2026; (b, f, j, n, r, v, z, dd) 2027–2038; and (c, g, k, o, s, w, aa, ee) 2039–2050. Non-stippled regions indicate at least 6 of the 8 models agree on the sign of the response. Subpolar North Atlantic (green box) time series includes the uncertainty (gray shading), estimated as the 90% confidence interval across models.

$0.04 \text{ mg m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for AFR; $-0.05 \pm 0.05 \text{ mg m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for EAS; and $-0.01 \pm 0.04 \text{ mg m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for SAS. The corresponding linear correlation with the AMOC responses (across experiments) is 1.0. Thus, perturbations that feature larger SDF decreases also feature larger AMOC weakening. Furthermore, the correlation between the AMOC and SDF responses across models is significant at the 90% confidence level for each experiment at $r = 0.95$ for GLO; 0.83 for NAE; 0.95 for AFR; 0.96 for EAS; and 0.73 for SAS. Thus, models that yield larger decreases in SDF also yield larger AMOC weakening.

Nearly all of the decrease in subpolar North Atlantic SDF is related to its thermal component (TSDF; **panels m–p**) (Hassan *et al* 2021, Robson *et al* 2022, Allen *et al* 2024, Lai *et al* 2025). The saline contribution (SSDF) is also negative but much weaker (supplementary figure 4). For example, the subpolar North Atlantic SSDF response under GLO for the last 12 years (2039–2050) is $-0.015 \pm 0.006 \text{ mg m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The corresponding decrease in TSDF is more than an order of magnitude larger at $-0.27 \pm 0.11 \text{ mg m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Similar conclusions apply for the regional aerosol perturbations. In the context of Arctic sea ice melt, it takes decade(s) for sea-ice induced freshwater to spread to the subpolar North Atlantic (Liu *et al* 2019, Liu and Federov, 2022). This implies changes in precipitation, evaporation, runoff and sea ice melt lead to relatively small decreases in SSDF (and in turn, SDF).

Further decomposing TSDF into its respective components shows that SW radiation (TSDF_{SW}; **panels q–t**) initiates the decrease in TSDF (see also supplementary figure 5), with maximum TSDF_{SW} reductions during the first (2015–2026) and second time period (2027–2038). The other components of TSDF, including LW radiation (TSDF_{LW}; **panels u–x**), latent heat flux (TSDF_{LH}; **panels y–bb**) and sensible heat flux (TSDF_{SH}; **panels cc–ff**), exhibit weak changes (which in some cases are positive; supplementary figure 5) during the first two time periods, but maximum reductions occur during the latter time period (2039–2050). These results are consistent with the importance of the AA reductions driving enhanced subpolar North Atlantic SW radiation and reduced TSDF_{SW} (and SDF) in the earlier time periods. For example, based on GLO, subpolar North Atlantic net SW radiation significantly increases in the first (2015–2026) and second (2027–2038) time periods at $0.56 \pm 0.22 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ and $1.12 \pm 0.56 \text{ W m}^{-2}$, respectively (supplementary figure 6). As mentioned above, this initiates AMOC weakening and subsequently leads to subpolar North Atlantic SST cooling via reduced poleward heat transport. This cooling in turn drives reductions in upwards surface LW radiation (increases in net LW) and increases in downwards surface turbulent heat fluxes. Based on GLO, subpolar North Atlantic net LW radiation, as well as downwards LH and SH, become progressively more positive, with maximum increases in the last (2039–2050) time period of $0.73 \pm 0.42 \text{ W m}^{-2}$, $2.2 \pm 1.2 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ and $2.0 \pm 0.81 \text{ W m}^{-2}$, respectively (Supplementary figure 6). These in turn result in decreased TSDF_{LW}, TSDF_{LH} and TSDF_{SH}, which help to maintain the overall decrease in SDF and in turn, AMOC weakening.

The response to Africa + Middle East AA reductions (figure 8) shows a tripolar North Atlantic SST pattern that peaks during 2027–2038 (figure 8(b)), including warming in the subtropics, cooling in the midlatitudes, and warming in the subpolar North Atlantic. Such a pattern has been related to the negative phase of the NAO, which is associated with weakening of the Azores high pressure and Icelandic low pressure, which in turn weakens the subpolar North Atlantic surface winds (Deser *et al* 2010). Supplementary figure 7 shows that these responses exist and are stronger in the four models that yield significant AMOC weakening for AFR (CanESM5-1, MRI-ESM2-0, NorESM2-LM, UKESM1-0-LL) as compared to the other four models that do not (CESM2, EC-Earth3-AerChem, MIROC6, CNRM-ESM2-1). For the former four models, sea level pressure decreases in the southern North Atlantic (15–50° N; 300–350° E) by $-0.12 \pm 0.05 \text{ hPa}$ and increases in the northern North Atlantic (55–80° N; 300–350° E) by $0.29 \pm 0.13 \text{ hPa}$, yielding a decrease in the meridional pressure gradient (southern minus northern North Atlantic) of $-0.41 \pm 0.16 \text{ hPa}$. A corresponding decrease in subpolar North Atlantic surface wind speeds also occurs at $-0.06 \pm 0.03 \text{ m s}^{-1}$. Weaker (and not significant) responses occur in the latter four models (those that do not yield significant AMOC weakening). Thus, AMOC weakening under AFR (in CanESM5-1, MRI-ESM2-0, NorESM2-LM, UKESM1-0-LL) appears to be related to a negative NAO-like response, which weakens subpolar North Atlantic winds and reduces turbulent heat loss from the ocean (supplementary figure 8 shows larger 2027–2038 TSDF_{LH} and TSDF_{SH} decreases in the four models with significant AMOC weakening versus the other four models), resulting in subpolar North Atlantic warming and reduced sea surface density. Outside of GLO (also during 2027–2038), the other AA perturbations do not yield a negative NAO-like response (supplementary figure 9). This lack of a NAO-like response includes EAS and SAS, which is dissimilar from that found in Liu *et al* (2024). There, a negative NAO-like response occurred in response to an increase in Asian anthropogenic aerosols, which weakened surface winds and heat fluxes in the subpolar North Atlantic.

Figure 9. EAS multimodel mean maps and subpolar North Atlantic time series. Panels show responses for (a)–(d) sea surface temperature (K); (e)–(h) sea surface salinity (psu); (i)–(l) surface density flux ($\text{mg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$); (m)–(p) thermal component of SDF ($\text{mg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$); (q)–(t) shortwave radiation component of TSDF ($\text{mg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$); (u)–(x) longwave radiation component of TSDF ($\text{mg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$); (y)–(bb) latent heat component of TSDF ($\text{mg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$); and (cc)–(ff) sensible heat component of TSDF ($\text{mg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$). Responses are shown for three 12 year time periods including (a, e, i, m, q, u, y, cc) 2015–2026; (b, f, j, n, r, v, z, dd) 2027–2038; and (c, g, k, o, s, w, aa, ee) 2039–2050. Non-stippled regions indicate at least 6 of the 8 models agree on the sign of the response. Subpolar North Atlantic (green box) time series includes the uncertainty (gray shading), estimated as the 90% confidence interval across models.

3.3. AMOC responses beyond 2050

We briefly comment on the AMOC response to AA reductions beyond 2050. Two models, CESM2 and UKESM1-0-LL, extended their RAMIP simulations through 2079. Both models show continued North Atlantic Ocean AOD decreases under all perturbations, with larger decreases from 2060–2079 relative to 2039–2050 in all cases except East Asia (supplementary table 3). Under global AA reductions, for example, CESM2 shows enhanced North Atlantic Ocean AOD decreases from $-9.0 \pm 0.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$ during 2039–2050 to $-9.7 \pm 0.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$ during 2060–2079. Similarly, UKESM1-0-LL yields corresponding AOD decreases of $-16.5 \pm 0.9 \cdot 10^{-3}$ and $-18.9 \pm 0.7 \cdot 10^{-3}$, respectively. Continued (and in most cases enhanced) reductions in North Atlantic Ocean AOD would be expected to drive continued weakening of the AMOC. In fact, Hassan *et al* (2021) shows that continued AMOC weakening beyond 2050 would be expected even if AOD anomalies do not continue to grow, because of a ~ 10 year delay of the AMOC response to AOD. Post-2050 AMOC weakening occurs for CESM2 (under all perturbations) but less so for UKESM1-0-LL. Under CESM2, global AA reductions yield enhanced AMOC weakening (nearly a doubling) from -1.8 ± 0.18 Sv during 2039–2050 to Sv during 2060–2079. Similarly, AMOC weakening more than doubles from 2039–2050–2060–2079 for East Asia, Africa + Middle East and North America + Europe AA reductions (supplementary table 3). Although UKESM1-0-LL also shows similar enhanced AMOC weakening under global AA reductions (92% larger weakening from 2060–2079 relative to 2039–2050), minor changes occur for the four regional perturbations. This difference is consistent with the fact CESM2 exhibited a relatively large AMOC response over our default time period of 2015–2050, whereas UKESM1-0-LL did not (e.g. figure 3). As discussed above, some of this intermodel difference is related to their AMOC climatology (e.g. figure 5), but other factors also likely contribute and warrant further investigation (e.g. relative importance of the AMOC-salt advection feedback).

4. Discussion and conclusions

Using RAMIP experiments, which compare an SSP3-7.0 (weak levels of air quality control) to an SSP1-2.6 (strong levels of air quality control) aerosol emission pathway, we have quantified the impact of global and regional aerosol reductions on the AMOC by mid-century (figure 2). GLO (figure 3(a)) yields the largest multimodel AMOC weakening at -0.98 ± 0.40 Sv by 2039–2050, with all 8 models yielding a decrease. NAE (figure 3(b)) yields the second largest multimodel mean AMOC weakening at -0.34 ± 0.18 Sv with 7 of the 8 models agreeing on a decrease. AFR (figure 3(c)) yields the next largest weakening at -0.22 ± 0.14 Sv with 7 of the 8 models yielding a decrease. This is followed by EAS (figure 3(d)) at -0.19 ± 0.18 Sv with 5 of the 8 models yielding a decrease and SAS (figure 3(e)) at -0.05 ± 0.13 Sv with 5 of the 8 models yielding a decrease. Assuming linearity, the sum of the AMOC weakening across the four regional perturbations represents the bulk (82%) of that under global AA reductions. In other words, AA emissions reductions for the rest-of-the-world account for a small percentage of the total weakening at 12%. This is consistent with the aerosol ERF, as most of the rest-of-the-world forcing is in the Pacific (Allen *et al* 2026).

The multimodel mean AMOC response (2039–2050) across experiments is consistent with the North Atlantic Ocean aerosol ERF (from fSST simulations), where $r = -0.95$ (figure 4(a)). Thus, aerosol perturbations that feature larger positive North Atlantic ERF are associated with larger AMOC weakening. A similar (but positive) correlation occurs between the AMOC response and North Atlantic Ocean AOD from coupled simulations ($r = 1.0$). We note that from a global perspective, AFR yields the weakest global mean aerosol ERF at $0.05 \pm 0.07 \text{ W m}^{-2}$, as compared to EAS, NAE and SAS with corresponding values of $0.15 \pm 0.07 \text{ W m}^{-2}$, $0.13 \pm 0.09 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ and $0.10 \pm 0.05 \text{ W m}^{-2}$, respectively (Allen *et al* 2026). Thus, it is the regional forcing (and the subsequent warming) as opposed to the global forcing that matters here. This is particularly evident for AFR, which has the second largest AMOC weakening, the smallest increase in global mean ERF, but the second largest increase in North Atlantic ERF.

All perturbations show a relatively large intermodel spread in AMOC response (e.g. figure 3). The intermodal spread in North Atlantic aerosol ERF does not consistently correlate to the corresponding intermodel AMOC spread (only GLO and NAE yield significant negative correlations). However, consistent with prior findings from CMIP6 (Weijer *et al* 2020), the intermodel AMOC spread in our simulations is related to each model's AMOC climatology (figure 5). Models that feature a stronger climatological AMOC are also associated with stronger AMOC weakening (figure 5; corresponding correlations are significant for GLO, NAE and EAS).

A deeper exploration of the mechanisms (figures 6–10) shows that AMOC weakening under AA reductions is associated with decreases in subpolar North Atlantic SDF, which are initiated by decreases in TSDF_{SW}, consistent with the positive North Atlantic forcing under aerosol reductions. These AA

forced AMOC weakening responses are subsequently reinforced by the AMOC-salt advection feedback. In some models, AFR AA reductions involve excitation of a negative NAO-like pattern (supp. figure 7), which weakens the subpolar North Atlantic surface winds and reduces surface turbulent heat fluxes (supp. figure 8), contributing to AMOC weakening. This is the case for the four models that yield significant AMOC weakening under AFR, including CanESM5-1, MRI-ESM2-0, NorESM2-LM, UKESM1-0-LL (figure 3(c)). The other four models lack both this dynamical response and significant AMOC weakening under AFR.

In contrast to the idealized simulations of Liu *et al* (2024), we do not find evidence for an AMOC response to East Asia or South Asia AA reductions that is opposite that from the other perturbations. We also note EAS and SAS lack a NAO-like response (supp. figure 9), which is dissimilar from that found in Liu *et al* (2024). There, a negative NAO-like response occurred in response to an increase in Asian anthropogenic aerosols, which weakened surface winds and heat fluxes in the subpolar North Atlantic. These differences are likely related to the lack of realistic aerosol forcing in Liu *et al* (2024), as they perturb SW radiation by a relatively large amount to mimic aerosol changes, i.e. 10% change in solar insolation over East Asia and South Asia. For Asia, this means a lot of the aerosol forcing over the Pacific in RAMIP experiments, largely due to aerosol-cloud interactions (e.g. Samset *et al* 2025; Allen *et al* 2026), is not accounted for in Liu *et al* (2024). This difference may be a key modifier of the Rossby wave train. A similar dynamical pathway was also found by Li and Liu (2025), again using a relatively large and idealized forcing (i.e. $10\times$ sulfate from PDRMIP simulations). About half of these PDRMIP simulations are concentration-based (as opposed to emissions-based), so they may suffer from the same shortcoming, i.e. lack of remote forcing, for example over the Pacific. Perhaps more fundamentally, the Rossby wave teleconnection may require a sufficiently strong forcing threshold (one that is not crossed using the more realistic and weaker aerosol forcings of RAMIP). According to Liu *et al* (2024), the 10% change in solar insolation (their idealized surrogate for an aerosol perturbation) results in an annual mean net radiative forcing of 30 W m^{-2} in the perturbation regions (i.e. East Asia and South Asia). Allen *et al* (2026) provides a comprehensive analysis of the RAMIP ERFs. The corresponding ERF in the RAMIP EAS perturbation (also annual mean over the EAS region) is $1.64 \pm 1.36 \text{ W m}^{-2}$. We note that this forcing is in response to a relatively large decrease (75%) in EAS SO_2 emissions. SAS yields a corresponding ERF (annual mean over the SAS region) of $1.61 \pm 1.0 \text{ W m}^{-2}$. Thus, the idealized aerosol perturbation in Liu *et al* (2024) is a factor of nearly $20\times$ larger. This suggests the different responses shown here (i.e. lack of a strong negative NAO teleconnection) is related to the smaller and more realistic aerosol forcing in RAMIP.

In contrast to the remote mechanism found in the idealized studies discussed above, RAMIP experiments show significant changes in aerosol related quantities over the North Atlantic (e.g. ERF in figure 1 and AOD in supp. figure 1). Such changes drive an increase in North Atlantic surface SW radiation (and decreased SDF), North Atlantic SST warming, and AMOC weakening. This shows the ability of atmospheric circulation to transport aerosols to the North Atlantic, even when they originate from afar (e.g. EAS). Furthermore, the multimodel mean AMOC responses across RAMIP experiments significantly correlate with these North Atlantic aerosol metrics (e.g. ERF and AOD in figure 4). Thus, our analysis shows the importance of atmospheric aerosol transport to the North Atlantic, which impacts the local surface SW radiative flux and subsequently the AMOC (with turbulent heat fluxes also contributing later on).

Global AA reductions yield AMOC weakening $1/3$ of that under the high-GHG SSP3-7.0 pathway. The similar magnitude of AMOC weakening across SSPs (Weijer *et al* 2020), despite large differences in their GHGs, is likely related to their different aerosol pathways (i.e. more aggressive AA reductions generally occur under the lower GHG pathways, which will promote AMOC weakening). Our results show that efforts to improve air quality, particularly in North America + Europe but also far away in East Asia, will contribute to future AMOC weakening.

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Data Availability Statement

The RAMIP data that supports the findings of this study are available through the Centre for Environmental Data Analysis (CEDA) archive at: <https://catalogue.ceda.ac.uk/uuid/4680fd74cf2244ba8476ed2617e3b41f/> (Wilcox 2026).

Supplementary data 1 available at: <https://doi.org/10.1088/2752-5295/ae63ef/data1>.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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